

FUNGAL RISK IN ASTROBIOLOGY: INVASIVE FUSARIOSIS IN THE IN VIVO MODEL GALLERIA MELLONELLA UNDER SIMULATED MICROGRAVITY.

Cottrel C.^{1,2,*}, Babin A-L¹, Machouart M-C.^{1,2}, Lozniewski A.^{1,2}, Fripiat J-P.¹, Debourgogne A.^{1,2,*}

¹UR SIMPA, Stress Immunity Pathogens Laboratory, Faculty of Medicine, Lorraine University, 9 avenue de la forêt de Haye, F-54500 Vandœuvre-lès-Nancy, France.

²Laboratoire de Microbiologie, CHRU de Nancy, Hôpitaux de Brabois, 11 allée du Morvan, 54511 Vandœuvre-lès-Nancy, France

claire.cottrel@univ-lorraine.fr (C.C.), anne-lyse.babin@univ-lorraine.fr (B. A-L.), marie-claire.machouart@univ-lorraine.fr (M.M-C.), alain.lozniewski@univ-lorraine.fr (L.A.), jean-pol.fripiat@univ-lorraine.fr (F.J-P.), anne.debourgogne@univ-lorraine.fr (D.A.).

Introduction:

Fusarium spp. are filamentous fungi widely distributed on Earth and also detected in space. After inhalation, this opportunistic pathogen can cause invasive fusariosis in humans including lung infections and fungemia. During space flights or Moon exploration, astronauts' immunity is impaired [1]: reduced T-cell activation and reduced phagocytosis capacity by neutrophils [2]. Of the various stresses encountered during spaceflights, microgravity can be studied by Random Positioning Machine on the ground. Previous studies have shown that microgravity increases the growth, spore production, and germination of *Fusarium spp. in vitro*, which suggests that the fungus becomes more pathogenic [3]. Given that *Fusarium spp.* has already been detected on the International Space Station [4] and was able to cause fusariosis in a plant [5], what about invasive fusariosis in Space?

Materials & Methods:

To investigate this question, the invertebrate model *Galleria mellonella* is infected with *Fusarium solani species complex (FSSC)* and exposed to microgravity simulated by the Random Positioning Machine (RPM). The random movements and velocity generated by the RPM device enable an average gravity close to zero ($g \approx 10^{-3}$) to be achieved. The fungus or the larva were also pre-exposed to RPM upstream of infection. For these experimental conditions, various parameters were monitored. Survival over time in normogravity ($g=1$) or RPM was assessed over 4 days. Fungal burden determination by qPCR was carried out following these infections [6].

Results:

Larvae infected with different strains of *FSSC* and exposed to RPM showed significantly higher mortality compared with larvae infected in normogravity (Log rank, $p < 0.0001$). Although virulence varied between strains (20% to 95% mortality), the mortality difference remains stable between the two conditions, with a 28% increase under simulated microgravity. To determine whether the origin of this susceptibility was host- or fungal related, pre-exposures of the larva or the fungus were performed. This led to higher mortality in both conditions, suggesting an impact of microgravity on fungal virulence and host

susceptibility. The fungal burden of *FSSC* appears to be increased during infection in simulated microgravity conditions.

Conclusions:

These results show an increased susceptibility to *Fusarium spp.* infection under spaceflight conditions. The *in vitro* and *in vivo* data are consistent with observations made for other molds where virulence was increased under microgravity conditions [7]. To go further, this experiment should be conducted in a moon-like partial gravity environment by RPM to study the pathophysiology of infection during lunar exploration or future habitation on the Moon.

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